

**EFFECTIVENESS OF SMET PROGRAMME WITH
RESPECT TO EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING OF
EXECUTIVES – AN EMPIRICAL STUDY**
Shatrughan Singh Naruka*, Vandana Rathore &
Mukesh Kumar Sharma*****

Jagadguru Ramanandacharya Rajasthan Sanskrit University, Mandau,
Jaipur, Rajasthan

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Abstract:

This is an initial attempt to study the effectiveness of Self Management of Excessive Tension (SMET) programme on emotional well-being of Executives. An empirical study was undertaken with sample size of 170 and out of which 12 subjects dropped out from “Salora” company in New Delhi. The sample consists of executives for middle and top levels. Subjects were divided into two groups -Yoga and Control group. Yoga group was given one month intervention of SMET programme for one hour every day. Emotional Quotient questionnaire developed by “N. K. Chadha” from Delhi University was used to measure the Emotional Quotient as an indicator of emotional well being. The result indicated that there is a significant difference between Yoga and Control group at 5% significance level. It implies that SMET intervention contributed to better emotional well being of the Executives

1. Introduction:

The opening up of the Indian economy through liberalization, privatization, globalization and natural thrust towards information technology has made the task of Indian Executives more demanding .The challenges get multiplied when the industry executives have to work in diversified cultures. The workforce diversity has not only affected the emotional stability of the executives but has also come on the way of leadership behavior and effectiveness. In a nutshell, tomorrow is the day of those industry executives who are more emotionally stable and show leadership effectiveness even in diverse circumstances. In the present study it is found that a person’s emotional intelligence level increases through self management of excessive tension (SMET) program. This program may helps in knowing all the five aspects of emotional intelligence of an individual. Developments in the field of emotional intelligence are progressing rapidly. Orme (2000) examines current developments in the U.K and internationally. She draws on current research and application for the organizations that are focusing on emotional intelligence and notes that the buzz around the subject of emotional intelligence is getting louder and louder. She in her article (2000) observes that: “Emotional Intelligence refers to the ability to use the emotion to help solve the problems and live in a more effective life. Emotion without intelligence and intelligence without emotion is only a part of solution. The complete solution is head working with the heart for organization. This definition confirms that all business decision has an element of emotional information for instances-what other people are feeling and how you are feeling in a particular situation-information that we can choose to ignore or work within its full richness in meaning. The time has come for Executives to open the emotional channels that remain untapped when we appeal solely to the rational and logical functions of the brain. Emotional intelligence is not crying openly in workplace, it is not talking about your personal life to the detriment of job. It is not permitting Executives to lash out at employees. It is not “letting out or hang out”.

Goleman (1996) introduced the concept of E.Q in his bestseller Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than I.Q .He gave the world a new meaning of emotional intelligence. According to Goleman, I.Q accounts only about 20% of a person’s success in life. The balance can be attributed to emotional intelligence or E.Q. Emotional intelligence is simply the intelligent use of emotions. The means of using ones emotional capacity in combination with ones intellectual, spiritual, psychological and other capacities. Goleman (1998b & 2001) defines emotional competence as a learned capability based on emotional intelligence that results in ability to represents our potential for achieving mastery of specific abilities. The emotional competencies themselves represent the degree to which an individual has mastered specific skills that allows the individual greater effectiveness in the workplace. Sexena and Kwatra observe that in an organization, growth is through its employees. Human capital in an organization is the most important asset and it is essential for the organization to help its human resources realize their potential for performing any job. For this, emotional intelligence as well as emotional quotient are needed. There are numerous instances where bright young b-school and engineering graduates with excellence track records are not able to replicate their success at the workplace. These people either didn’t possess adequate emotional competence and or the organization didn’t take timely and effective

measures to develop the requisite emotional competencies in them. Thus they were not able to realize their potential and had burnouts due to over stress; lack of polarization, etc. Emotional intelligence quotient has been referred interchangeably with other conceptually similar concepts such as general intelligence factor. I.Q is a measure of one's cognitive abilities, whereas emotional intelligence involves being aware of emotions and how they can affect and interact with traditional intelligence. It includes the following domains:

- ✓ Self Awareness
- ✓ Self Regulation
- ✓ Motivation
- ✓ Empathy
- ✓ Social Skills

Duraiswamy (www.eiconsortium.org) observes that the "Emotional Intelligence is an ability to understand one's own feelings, empathy for the feelings of others, and Managing emotions in a way to enhance living. These are important qualities for the both personal and work life balance. Language remains unconsciousness until it is dealt with emotionally. Emotional intelligence is a tool that evokes consciousness of the language being learnt, enabling the learner to understand, clarify and communicate ideas". Emmerling and Goleman (2003) note that there have been three general approaches to emotional intelligence, represented by Reuven-Bar-On, Daniel Goleman, and Jack Mayer and Peter Salovey. Looking at the origins of the work of these teams is illuminating. Reuven Bar-On approach is on a concept called subjective well-being and non-intellectual aspects of performance. Daniel Goleman was a student of David Mc-Clelland, one of the most influential psychologists in the area of competencies. For historical purpose we can start the countdown of emotional intelligence in 1990 (the year of seminal Salovey and Mayer article) or 1996 (the year of the best selling Goleman Book). Jack Mayer was trained in both clinical and experimental psychology and worked in the areas of human intelligence as well as cognitive and affect (how emotions and thinking interact). His colleague Peter Salovey had similar interest in cognition and affect and its various applications especially to health psychology.

The idea of E.Q is also closely related with the idea of H.Q.Q (Human Quality Quotient) suggested by Subhash Sharma (1996) in his book *Management in New Age-Western Windows Eastern Doors*. H.Q.Q is based on Thought-Action (TA) framework and suggests that good thought-action leads to further positive emotions and positive energy. Negative thought-action leads to negative emotions and negative energy. This suggests that E.Q can be E.Q positive and E.Q negative. E.Q positive represents positive use of emotions and E.Q negative represents negative use of emotions e.g. terrorism etc. In general, E.Q is understood only as E.Q positive.

2. SMET:

SMET is a set of techniques developed by SVYASA (Swami Vivekananda Yoga Anusandhana Samsthana, 1986) Bangalore. As we know everybody is having or carrying some amount of tension with her or himself. Hence, the name of the technique is SMET. SMET programmes are conducted in different locations throughout the country and are attended by executives and others with excessive tension. SMET stands for Self Management of Excessive Tension. This programme consists of theory as well as the practical sessions. The theory part consists of six lecture sessions. They are as follows: introduction to Stress programme, introduction to stress, executive growth, group dynamics, stress physiology and SVYASA research. The practical part consists of practices related to Executive tension which is also known as "Cyclic - Meditation". The practical part also consists of some asana including three relaxation techniques, which are as follows—

- ✓ I.R.T-Instant Relaxation Technique
- ✓ Q.R.T-Quick Relaxation Technique
- ✓ D.R.T-Deep Relaxation Technique

The practical part of "Cyclic Meditation" is a combination of Stimulation and Relaxation, where relaxation period is longer than Stimulation. This practice is based upon two principles:

- ✓ Depth of Perception
- ✓ Expansion of Awareness

In general participating executives have reported improvement in efficiency at work. In addition they have experienced other benefits like:

- ✓ Reduction in blood pressure
- ✓ Steep decreases in the consumption of the tranquilizers
- ✓ Clarity in thinking and
- ✓ Relaxed feeling in action

In our study we have used SMET practice as an instrument of change in the level of emotional well-being and emotional intelligence. (See Appendix-1)

3. Indian Experience in Measuring Emotional Intelligence:

The use of psychological measurement has always been somewhat controversial, and the measurement of theories within the emotional intelligence paradigm is no different. Emotional intelligence as we use the term

here refers to about two dozen social and emotional abilities that previous research has shown to be linked to successful performance in the workplace. The primary focus for research on social intelligence was to see whether it could be distinguished from academic intelligence, but researchers have experienced failure for many times. Hence, they started to move on to the new ventures (Hedlund and Stenber, 2000), Social intelligence as a type of emotional intelligence was not easily demonstrable (Wechsler, 1958), and it remained undefined and unmeasured (Cronback, 1960). Mayer and Salovey (1993) believed that emotional intelligence may have better discriminative validity than social intelligence, and may be more distinguishable from general intelligence. In scientific psychology, the proper understanding of a construct becomes very important for the development of its test. Based on the observation of much useful measurement of intelligence quotient and personality, Thingujian (2002) expressed his belief that ability model of emotional intelligence, although originated in the West, can be applied effectively in the Indian context. Orme (2000) observes that the MEIS (Multi -Factor Emotional Intelligence Test) is defined as an ability measure of emotional intelligence. It measures ability across four branches of emotional intelligence, which are combined to yield a total emotional intelligence score. These four branches are:

- ✓ Identifying Emotions
- ✓ Using Emotions
- ✓ Understanding Emotions
- ✓ Managing Emotions

This test measures through 12 sets of exercise contained with a paper and pencil test. The next generation MEIS has several refinements and is known as MSCEIT (The Mayer and Salovey Caruso Emotional Intelligence test). An ability test if designed scientifically should provide systematic, objective and standardized samples of the performance of a task (Magill, 1999). More important test to measure the emotional intelligence in India should be ability test like MSCEIT. It tests ability which assesses demonstrable skills or knowledge.

Emotional Intelligence behaviors inherent in our culture should be reflected in the context of emotional intelligence scale. It might be worth to remember what Wechsler (1958) said about the difference between intelligence and intelligence behavior. Emotional Intelligence researcher should keep in mind that ours is predominantly collectivistic culture, whereas there is individualistic culture in U.S.A. The world today is undergoing a change more profound and far reaching than any experienced since dawn of the modern age. Emotional intelligence suggests that high levels of emotional intelligent leaders create a climate in which information sharing, trust, health, risk taking and learning flourish. The cost effectiveness of emotional intelligence is a relatively new idea for business. Emmerling, R.J. & Goleman, D. (2003) many said they feared that feeling empathy or compassion for those they worked with would put them in conflict with their organizational goals. They felt that idea of sensing the feelings of those who worked for him was assured it would, he said “be impossible to deal with people” other protested that if they were not emotionally aloof they would be unable to make the hard decisions that business requires although the likelihood is that they would deliver those decisions more humanely”.

On the positive side, the benefits of being skilled in the basic emotional competence are being attuned to the feeling of those being dealt with, being able to handle disagreements so they do not escalate and having the ability to get into flow states while doing our work. Leadership is not domination, but the art of persuading people to work towards a common goal. And in the terms of our managing our own career, there may be nothing more essential than recognizing our deepest feeling about what we do and what changes might make us more truly satisfied with work. Table -1 sums up the above discussions.

Table 1: Ideal & Non-Ideal Leadership

Ideal Leadership	High Emotional Competency/E.Q	High task competence
Non- Ideal Leadership	Low Emotional Competency/E.Q	Low task competence

4. The Instrument to Measure the Emotional Well-Being Among Executives:

In this study we have used the instrument developed by N. K. Chadha. This test was made by compiling real life situations experienced by individuals in their day to day life. The situations were selected to avoid response bias such as “faking - good” or “social desirability tendency” by the respondents. In this test only such situations which have been deemed relatively neutral with regard to social desirability tendency were introduced. The situations reflect some areas of emotional intelligence such as self awareness, self regulation, handling relationships, motivation, conflict resolution and stress management. The samples were drawn from different sections of the society. The age range of the subjects was 18 to 50 years. They were Executives, executive from public or private sector, teachers from college and universities and from other professions such as nursing, accountancy, engineering, banking and medicine, information technology, police, business, politics and insurance. Psychologists have studied that it is possible to measure the emotional characteristics of an individual by using psychological tests. The most important step in making a psychological test is its standardization. This involves situation selection, situation analysis and critically evaluating the reliability and

validity of test in given parameters. This is the first time that a test to measure the emotional intelligence has been developed for the Indian population.

Like any other psychological test, E.Q test also has its share of criticism. There are numerous E.Q tests which measure the emotional climate such as – pleasure-displeasure, arousal-nonarousal, or dominance-submission. Other test evaluate “emotional empathy “i.e., feeling what other feel among various scale is the affiliative tendency scale, which measures skills like friendliness, sociability, helpfulness, and skills essentials for dealing with people. The scale also measures facts of adjustment and high emotional intelligence (e.g.), affiliativeness, achievement, arousal of stimulus seeking, extroversion, optimism, empathy, nurturance and sensuousness. Emotional intelligence includes the ability to accurately perceive your own emotions and those of others, exercise mastery over your emotions and behaviors and respond appropriately in various life situations, enter into relationship with an honest expressions of emotions, select work which is emotionally rewarding, thereby avoiding procrastination, self doubt and low achievement, and balance work, home and recreational life. It may be indicated that Chadha’s emotional intelligence test for the Indian population has been standardized on Indian Executives, business, bureaucrats and industrial workers. Hence, it was used in this study. This test consisted of 15 questions based on 5 point scale rating and then finally obtained scores that was converted into percentile score. This has been shown in the interpretation table:

Interpretation of Scores:

Score	Percentile	Interpretations
285 and Above	P - 90	Extremely High E.Q
250 - 274	P - 75	High E.Q
200 - 249	P - 50	Moderate E.Q
150 - 199	P - 40	Low E.Q
149 and below	P - 15	Try Some Other Day

5. The Design of the Study:

5.1 A Randomized Control Design:

Sample: The sample consisted of 170 middle and top class and middle class employees from “Salora” company, the age range were between 25 to 50 years ages. The rank structure for the respondents varied from engineer to deputy Executives, and length of service ranged between 5 to 20 years. Total sample size (170) was divided into two groups- Yoga group (85) and Control group (85).

5.2 Data Extraction or Variables: E.Q has been measured by using the emotional quotient questionnaire where 15questions are asked for 15 situations developed by N. K. Chadha.

5.3 Yoga Intervention: In our study we have used SMET program as an instrument of change in the level of emotional intelligence. E.Q test was administered to all the members participating in this study, before the intervention and after the intervention. The intervention which was given to yoga group was SMET (self management of excessive tension) programme, which consists of six lecture sessions as well as practical class for one hour every day, whereas control group was given only half an hour walking everyday in the evening, and told them to write diary about their improvement.

6. Data Analysis:

Data analysis was done by using S.P.S.S 10.0 version and Kolmogrov –Spharo, independent T test of pre data, paired T test between the group and finally independent T test of post data were conducted.

Result: Results are presented in tables 2, 3, 4 and 5.

Table 2: Mean Value

Group	Pre – E.Q Score	Post – E.Q Score	% Change / (post pre/ pre*100)
Yoga Group	200.62	241	19.69%
Control Group	201.49	186.19	-11.54%

Table 3: Test of Normality

Group	E.Q Score	Sig.
Yoga	Pre. E.Q Score	0.087
Control	Pre. E.Q Score	.200*

Table 4: Paired Sample T- Test

Group	Sig. (2 –tailed)
Yoga Group (Pre E.Q Score – Post E.Q Score)	.000 (Significant Improvement)
Control Group (Pre E.Q Score – Post E.Q Score)	.000 (Significant Detoriation)

Table 5: Independent Sample Test (t-test for equity of means)

Group		Sig. (2-tailed)
Pre E.Q Score	Equal variances assumed	0.180
	Equal variances not assumed	0.180

Post E.Q Score	Equal variances assumed	.000
	Equal variances not assumed	.000

7. Conclusion:

Data were found to be normally distributed (Yoga $-.087 > .05$, control $-.200^* > .05$). Data were found homogenous (Yoga $-.180 > .05$, control $-.180 > .05$), based on these two parametric test (paired T test). There was significant difference between Yoga and Control group. Independent T test was done by using post data and there was a significant difference found, (Yoga $-.000 > .05$, Control $-.000 > .05$). Table-2 shows that average value has come down in Control Group from the value of 241.00 to 186.19, where as in Yoga Group average value has gone up from 200.62 to 210.49. Table-4 presents the result of Paired t-test, which shows that there is a highly significant result in Positive direction in Yoga Group (significant improvement), where as in Control Group there is also significant result but in negative direction (significant deterioration). Finally, Table -5 presents the result of Independent t-test (Between Group), there is no significant result in Base line data, whereas there is a significant change in Post data.

Limitations: The limitations of this study are as follows:

- ✓ In this study only one month intervention was given. Intervention period can be increased.
- ✓ Only one company /organization was studied. Different companies' studies can be done. This could give stronger findings.
- ✓ All the respondents were male. Female member should be included to find out whether it can be applicable for both male and female members.

Suggestions: This study is an initial study in this field and a more detailed study should be done to measure the link between SMET and E.Q and to measure the instrument of SMET programme effectiveness on emotional well being among executives in general.

8. Summary:

Focus of this study was on effectiveness of self management of excessive tension (SMET) program on emotional well-being of Executives. Empirical data for the study was collected from the executives of Salora Company from New Delhi. Executives were divided into two groups; viz, Yoga Group and Control Group. Yoga group was given SMET exercise. E.Q as an indicator of emotional well-being was measured on the basis of questionnaire designed by Chadha. The empirical results indicated that SMET interventions contributed to the emotional well-being of the Executives who participated in this study.

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